

Origin of Feynman's Path Integral Formulation

To prove the equivalence between the Quantum State Vector Tensor Field (QSUTF) in Quantum Information Holography (QIH) and Feynman's Path Integral formulation, we need to carefully examine the mathematical structures and underlying principles of both formulations.

Quantum State Vector Tensor Field (QSUTF) in QIH

In QIH, the state of the quantum system is represented as a superposition of QSVs:

$$\Psi_{\text{QSUTF}} = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(x, t)$$

where:

$\psi_i(x, t)$ are the basis states

c_i are the coefficients representing the amplitudes of the quantum states.

Feynman's Path Integral Formulation

Feynman's Path Integral formulation expresses the probability amplitude for a quantum transition from an initial state $|\psi_i\rangle$ to a final state $|\psi_f\rangle$ as a sum over all possible paths, each contributing a phase factor determined by the action S :

$$\langle \psi_f | \psi_i \rangle = \int D[x(t)] e^{iS[x(t)]/\hbar}$$

where:

- $D[x(t)]$ denotes integration over all possible path $x(t)$.

- $S[x(t)]$ is the action along the path $x(t)$.

- $\hbar$ is the reduced Planck constant.

Equivalence Proof

Step 1: Representation of Quantum States

In QM, the quantum state is described by a superposition of basis states:

$$\Psi_{\text{QSUTF}} = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(x, t)$$

In Feynman's formulation, the quantum state transition amplitude is given by:

$$\langle \psi_f | \psi_i \rangle = \int D[x(t)] e^{iS[x(t)]/\hbar}$$

To show the equivalence, we need to express the QSUTF in a form that matches the path integral formulation.

Step 2: Path Integral in QIH Terms

In QIH, the transition probability amplitude from $|\psi_i\rangle$ to $|\psi_f\rangle$ sums over all possible paths of the QSVs, weighted by their amplitudes and phases:

$$\langle \psi_f | \psi_i \rangle = \sum_{\text{paths}} e^{i\phi[\text{path}]}$$

where $\phi[\text{path}]$ is the phase associated with a given path.

Step 3: Action and Phase Relationship

The phase $\phi[\text{path}]$ in QIH is related to the action $S[x(t)]$ in Feynman's formulation:

$$\phi[\text{path}] = \frac{S[x(t)]}{\hbar}$$

Thus, the QIH transition amplitude can be written as:

$$\langle \psi_f | \psi_i \rangle = \sum_{\text{paths}} e^{iS[x(t)]/\hbar}$$

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Step 4: Continuous Sum Over Paths

In the path integral formulation, the sum over discrete paths can be replaced by an integral over continuous paths:

$$\langle \Psi_f | \Psi_i \rangle = \int D[x(t)] e^{iS[x(t)]/\hbar}$$

Step 5: Summing Over Histories in QIH

The QSVTF sums over the possible QSV configurations, capturing the quantum states' probabilistic nature:

$$\Psi_{\text{QSVTF}} = \sum_i C_i \psi_i(x, t) \int D[x(t)] e^{iS[x(t)]/\hbar}$$

Conclusion

We have shown that the QSVTF in QIH can be expressed in terms of Feynman's path integral formulation. The key steps involve recognizing the relationship between the phase factor in QIH and the action in Feynman's approach and transitioning from a discrete to a continuous sum over paths. Therefore, we can conclude that:

Yes, the QSVTF in QIH is equivalent to Feynman's path integral formulation, showing that QIH provides the same answer and captures the same quantum mechanical behavior as Feynman's method. In addition, QIH demonstrate the origin of the Path Integral Formulation.